

Biosilica co-entrapment of MNPs and enzyme

1. AIM

Generation of biomimetic silica nanohybrids containing both magnetic nanoparticles and enzyme.

2. SCOPE

This protocol is defined to carry out the formation of nanohybrids of the enzyme of interest and MNPs using biomimetic silica as encapsulating strategy (BioSi@Enz-MNPs). The entrapment protocol has been optimized for the enzyme horseradish peroxidase (HRP) which is a glycosylated enzyme. Thus, take in mind that for other enzymes you may do some adjustments to several parameters (enzyme, MNPs and /or Polyethyleneimine (PEI) ratio, PEI size, pH) to obtain optimal entrapment yields.

In the case of glycosylated enzymes, a previous oxidation step of the enzyme's sugar chains may be needed to improve the co-entrapment yield and increase the thermal stability. See Annex 1 "Case study 1: HRP&MNPs co-entrapment", for details in this additional previous step to be carried out before the general co-entrapment protocol.

An additional blocking step of the BioSi@hybrids could be carried out if the neutralization of their positive surface is needed. In the case of HRP&entrapment this has been optimized taking advantage of the need of a previous oxidation of the enzyme sugar chains. See Annex 1 "Case study 1: HRP&MNPs co-entrapment", for details in this additional post-encapsulation step if needed.

The total volume of a single nanohybrid is 550 uL, for preparing other amount of nanohybrids, the volume of the reagents can be directly extrapolated (direct proportionality).

3. DEFINITIONS

Initial activity

It is expressed as the activity of the enzyme contained in the initial volume of enzyme added in reaction, i.e. Activity in Units present in the 40 uL added in reaction.

Immobilization yield

It is expressed as the percentage of the ratio of the difference between the initial activity offered in the entrapment reaction and the activity recovered in the supernatant after the encapsulation had took place versus the initial activity offered (Equation 1).

$$\% I = \frac{\text{Initial activity} - \text{Activity in supernatant}}{\text{Initial activity}} * 100 \quad (1)$$

Expressed activity (EA)

It is defined as the percentage of the ratio between the activity immobilized onto the support and the activity offered to the carrier (Equation 2).

$$\% EA = \frac{\text{Activity in immobilized preparation}}{\text{Initial activity} - \text{Activity in supernatant}} * 100 \quad (2)$$

4. MATERIALS

- 2 mL eppendorf (Eppendorf).
- 15 mL and 50 mL Falcon Tubes.

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- Pipettes and tips

5. REAGENTS

- Polyethylenimine (PEI) (MW 1300, Sigma Aldrich 482595-100ML)
- Dibasic sodium phosphate (Sigma Aldrich S7907-1KG)
- Tetramethyl orthosilicate (Sigma Aldrich, 341436-25G)
- Trehalose (Sigma Aldrich 1.08216.0100, 100-G)
- Sodium borohydride (Sigma Aldrich, 452882-25G)
- Magnetic nanoparticles (CSIC9¹, CSIC23¹)

Note 1: Original carboxylated MNPs, without being modified with NTA-moieties on their surface.

- Enzyme of interest

6. SOLUTIONS

- 0.1 M sodium phosphate, pH 8.0
- 5 mM sodium phosphate, pH 8.0
- 5 mM sodium phosphate pH 8.0 with 300 mM Trehalose
- 0.1 M sodium phosphate with 300 mM NaCl, pH 8.0
- Enzyme stock solution (1 mg/mL²) in 0.1 M sodium phosphate buffer, pH 8.0.

Note 2: Protein concentration measured using the molar extinction coefficient of the protein or other protein determination techniques (Bradford, BCA...)

- 10% of PEI 1200 g/mol
- 1M hydrolysed TMOS in 1 mM HCl.

7. EQUIPMENTS

- End-over-end stirrer
- Vortex
- Sonication water bath
- Benchtop centrifuge for Eppendorf that can reach 13500 x g (Eppendorf Centrifuge MiniSpin plus)

8. PROCEDURE

8.1 PREPARATION OF ~~10% PEI SOLUTION for 40 mL FINAL VOLUME~~

This amount of PEI should be sufficient for 800 samples.

1. Weight ~~10.8 g~~ of PEI (50 wt %) by pipetting directly into a 50 mL falcon tube³.

Note 3: Be careful while weighting PEI as it is very thick. Weight directly in the 50 mL falcon tube with the help of a spatula. The use of a plastic Pasteur can be a valid alternative to a spatula.

2. Suspend the PEI in 25 mL of 0.1 M Sodium phosphate buffer pH 8.0 using a magnetic stirrer.
3. Place the solution in an ice bath.
4. Adjust the pH to 8.0 using 6M HCl under magnetic stirring.

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Note 4: HCl should NOT be added at one time as it can lead to oxidation of the primary amino moieties of PEI due to heating of the suspension. Thus, add HCl solution dropwise making sure the PEI solution stays cold after each addition.

Note 5. You can adjust the pH of the PEI solution by maintaining the solution in ice and adding the HCl dropwise. At the end of the procedure, wait to have the solution at room temperature and check for the pH. Adjust it if necessary.

5. Wait until the pH 8.0 is stable for at least 10 minutes.

Note 6. It could take at least 30 minutes to obtain a stable pH value.

6. Adjust the volume up to ~~40 mL~~ with 0.1 M Sodium phosphate buffer pH 8.0 if necessary.
7. Store at 4°C temperature protected from light for 4-5 weeks.

Note 7. To protect from light the solution, use an amber flask or wrapped a transparent one with aluminum foil. If the PEI solution turns yellow, during preparation as well as during storage, it should be discarded.

8.3 PREPARATION OF MNPs suspension.

1. Sonicate the particles for 10 minutes.
2. Dilute the particles in 0.1 M sodium phosphate buffer pH 8.0 at a concentration of 9 mg/mL.

Note 8. It is not necessary to add ice in the sonication bath, the temperature is not a fundamental parameter at this point.

8.4 PREPARATION OF BioSi@MNPS-Enzyme.

1. Weight the Eppendorf you are going to use, so that at the end of the procedure you can calculate the amount of silica support you have generated.

Note 9. For a better pellet formation, use, if possible, Eppendorf tubes of 2 mL with round bottom.

2. Mix gently 40 µL of protein (1 mg/mL) with 400 µL of 5 mM Sodium phosphate buffer pH 8.0 containing 300 mM Trehalose into a 2 mL Eppendorf tube.
3. Add 50 µL PEI 10% and mix gently by pipetting.
4. Incubate for 15 minutes under top-bottom stirring at room temperature.
5. During the 15 minutes incubation, prepare the hydrolysed TMOS.

- a. Pipette slowly 154 µL of tetramethyl orthosilicate (TMOS) in 1 mL of 1 mM hydrochloric acid. Do it in a do it in fume hood, gloves and goggles needed. TMOS is highly toxic!

Note 10: When adding the TMOS you will see a colourless pellet, resuspend it by pipetting five times. You will see that the pellet disappears, and some bubbles suddenly appear. That is the hydrolysis of the TMOS.

- b. Vortex the sample for 30 seconds.
- c. Leave for 15 min at room temperature.

Note 11: hydrolysed TMOS cannot be stored. It should be freshly prepared.

6. Add 44 µL of the MNPs (9 mg/mL) suspension (See Annex 2 for MNPs characteristics).
7. Add 100 µL of hydrolysed TMOS by slowly pipetting it into the suspension of PEI and enzyme.

Note 12: you should pipette three times the reaction mixture.

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Note13: You should start to see a dull solution after 3-5 minutes. In Figure 1 you can see an example of silica precipitation without MNPs after the addition of hydrolysed TMOS.

Figure 1. A: samples containing sodium phosphate buffer and 10% PEI before the addition of hydrolysed TMOS and **B:** samples after the addition of the TMOS.

8. Let the Eppendorf rest for 30 minutes without shaking it (see Figure 2A).
9. Centrifuge for 5 minutes at 13500 × g and collect the supernatant and store it for further use.

Note 14. We DO NOT suggest magnetization for the separation of the nanohybrids.

10. Resuspend in 400 μL of 0.1 M sodium phosphate buffer containing 300 mM NaCl, pH 8.0 (see Figure 2B).

11. Incubate for 15 min in an end-over-end stirrer at 4 °C.

12. Wash four times by centrifugation for 5 minutes at 13500 × g and resuspend in 0.1 M sodium phosphate buffer pH 8.0.

13. Collect the supernatant and store it for the determination of immobilization yield and expressed activity.

Note 15. The use of all colorimetric assays for protein determination is not possible do to PEI interference, immobilization yield and expressed activity have to be expressed using activity measurements.

14. Resuspend the preparation in 400 μL of 0.1 M sodium phosphate buffer.

Note 16. We suggest storing in sodium phosphate buffer and not in working solution as the particle structure and stability can be affected do to a change in pH and ionic strength if stored for a long time in other buffer solutions.

15. Sonicate the preparation for 5 min in water bath.

16. Store at 4 °C.

Figure 2. A: samples after adding TMOS and **B:** samples after centrifugation for 5 min at 13500 x g. In this example, each preparation has been done with HRP and different MNPs named as MNP1-3.

ANNEX 1: CASE STUDY 1: HRP&MNPs CO-ENTRAPMENT

A) PRE-ENCAPSULATION STEP: OXIDATION OF HRP PROTOCOL.

1. AIM

To enhance the stability and improve the entrapment yield of the soluble HRP. This is a heavily glycosylated enzyme thus in order to enhance entrapment and 3D rigidification (via a post-encapsulation step), aldehyde groups are introduced into its sugar chains by oxidation using sodium periodate.

2. SCOPE

This protocol is a modification of Zalipsky's PEGylation protocol and is defined to obtain a 1 mg/mL solution of oxidized HRP.

3. MATERIALS

- 1 and 2 mL eppendorf (Eppendorf).
- PD-10 Desalting Column (GE Healthcare).
- Pipettes and tips.
- Amicon 10 K.

4. REAGENTS

- Horseradish peroxidase (HRP) Type VI (EC 1.11.1.7) (#P8375-5KU)
- Dibasic sodium phosphate (Sigma Aldrich S7907-1KG)
- Sodium periodate (Pancreac, 131700.1208)
- Glycerol (Pancreac, 141339.1211)
- Distilled water

5. SOLUTIONS

- 10 mM sodium phosphate containing 154 mM sodium chloride, pH 7.2.
- 0.1 M sodium phosphate pH 7.2 containing 154 mM sodium chloride
- 0.1 M sodium phosphate, pH 8.0

6. EQUIPMENT

End-over-end stirrer.

7. PROCEDURE

1. Dissolve 3 mg of Horseradish Peroxidase (HRP) in 1.8 mL of 10 mM sodium phosphate containing 154 mM sodium chloride, pH 7.2.
2. Dissolve 8.6 mg of sodium periodate in 200 μ L of distilled water and protected from light.
3. Add the sodium periodate solution immediately to the enzyme solution and agitate gently.
4. Incubate the mixture in the dark for 1 h at 25 $^{\circ}$ C with constant agitation.
5. Quench the reaction by adding 2.5 μ L of glycerol.

Note: The oxidized enzyme is noted as HRPox.

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6. Purified the oxidized enzyme by using a desalting PD10 column.
 - a. Column equilibration is performed by adding three times 4 mL of 0.1 M sodium phosphate pH 7.2 containing 154 mM sodium chloride (equilibration buffer).
 - b. Add 1 mL of HRPox (previously prepared). Then, add 1.5 mL of 0.1 M sodium phosphate pH 8.0 and discard the supernatant. Next, add 2 mL more of 0.1 M sodium phosphate pH 8.0 and collect the supernatant.
7. Concentrate to 1 mg/mL with Amicon 10 K at 4000 x g for 5 minutes.

B)- POST-ENCAPSULATION STEP: 3D RIGIDIFICATION NPS SURFACE

1. AIM.

In the case of glycosylated enzymes this step allows to trigger a three-dimensional covalent rigidification of the protein structure.

1. Following the entrapment, incubate the nanohybrids in 400 μ L of 25 mM sodium bicarbonate, pH 10.0 overnight in agitation at 4°C.

Note1: This facilitates the formation of Schiff's bases between the aldehyde groups generated in the enzyme (see annex 1: pre-encapsulation step) and unreacted amino groups from the support.

2. Wash by centrifugating for 5 minutes at 13500 \times g and resuspend in 0.4 mL of sodium borohydride (1mg/mL). Incubate for 30 min at room temperature.

Note2: During this incubation Schiff's bases are reduced and thus a covalent stable amide bond is formed.

3. Washed twice by centrifugating for 5 minutes at 13500 \times g and resuspend in 0.1 M sodium phosphate buffer pH 8.0.

Note3: Before the second wash, weight the Eppendorf with their respective pellets and calculate the amount of generated silica support.

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ANNEX 2: MAGNETIC NANOPARTICLES CHARACTERISTICS

	Synthesis	Coating	Functional groups	TEM (nm)/PDI	DH (nm)/PDI	Z potential (mV)
CSIC-9	Co-precipitation	DMSA	-COOH	12	117/0.2	-26
CSIC-23	Thermal decomposition	PMAO	-COOH	15	111/0.18	-30

ANNEX 3: CHARACTERIZATION OF THE NANOHYBRIDS

1. DLS AND Z-POTENTIAL

Dynamic light scattering (DLS) was performed in Milli-Q water at a sample concentration of 0.1 mg/mL of dry support on a 90 Plus Particle Size Analyzer (Brookhaven Instrument), using ten runs of 20 seconds per measurement at 25 °C.

Z-potential measurements were performed in 1 mM KCl pH 7.4 at a sample concentration of 0.02 mg/mL of dry support respectively for a final volume of 0.2 mL on a 90 Plus Particle Size Analyzer (Brookhaven Instrument).

2. DETERMINATION OF THE ENTRAPPED IRON CONCENTRATION

The iron determination is performed on the nanohybrid to determine the concentration of entrapped MNPs.

a. MATERIAL

- 1.5 mL graduated microtubes
- Pipettes and pipette tips with filters
- 96-well plates
- Graduated cylinders
- Borosilicate glass bottles / vials
- Spatulas

b. REAGENTS

- Nanosuspension to be analysed
- Aqua Regia (see paragraph 5.1 for aqua regia preparation)
- Milli-Q water
- Trisodium phosphate
- Potassium hydroxide
- Tiron

c. SOLUTIONS

- Trisodium phosphate (Na_3PO_4), 0.2 M solution in water, pH 9.7
- Potassium hydroxide (KOH), 4 N solution in water
- Tiron (1,2-dihydroxybenzen-3,5-disulfonic acid)
- Iron standard solution, for atomic adsorption spectroscopy, 1 mg/mL Fe in 2 to 5% HNO_3

d. EQUIPMENTS

- Precision balance
- Fume hood
- Dry heating bath (heating block) for 2 mL microtubes (placed inside the fume hood)
- Multiskan Go spectrophotometer (Thermo Scientific) – the same SOP can be easily adapted to other brands of spectrophotometers
- Computer

1. Switch on the heating block and set the temperature at 60 °C.

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2. Prepare standard solutions¹ of Fe(III) in milli-Q water at different concentrations (0², 100, 200, 400, 600 and 800 µg/mL) starting from the commercially available iron standard solution (concentration 1 mg/mL).

Note 1: Prepare each sample in triplicates.

Note 2: The sample of concentration 0 µg/mL is Milli-Q water.

3. Place 50 µL of each standard solution in a 1.5 mL graduated microtube
4. Prepare the samples to be analysed by mixing 5-10 µL of nanohybrids³ suspension with 45/40⁴ µL of milli-Q water (3 microtubes for each sample).

Note 3: Sonicate the nanohybrids for 5 minutes and resuspend properly until you see a homogeneous suspension.

Note 4: In most instances, this sample dilution is necessary and must be taken into account for the measurement and for the calculation of the concentration.

5. Once all samples are prepared, add 100 µL of aqua regia to each microtube to reach a final volume of 150 µL, close the lids, place the microtubes in the dry heating bath⁵ and maintain at 60 °C for 15 minutes.

Note 5: Before placing the microtubes in the dry heating bath, practice a small perforation in the lid of each microtube using a needle or use vented cap eppendorfs.

6. During the 15 minutes of heating, prepare a 0.25 M Tiron solution in Milli-Q water, calculating 10 µL per sample⁶.

Note 6: Always prepare a slight excess of Tiron solution.

7. Mix the 10 µL of 0.25 M Tiron solution (per sample) with the 50 µL of 4 N KOH solution (per sample).
8. After completion of the 15 minutes at 60 °C, add 350 µL of Milli-Q water to each microtube and transfer 50 µL of the resulting solution from each microtube to a 96-well plate.

Note 7: remember to prepare a blank solution containing only Tiron

9. To each well, add 60 µL of the 0.25 M Tiron + 4 N KOH solution prepared in Step 8 and 100 µL of the 0.2 M Na₃PO₄ solution in water, pH 9.7.

Note 8: Use the same pipette tip for adding the 60 µL of the 0.25 M Tiron + 4 N KOH solution to the three samples with the same concentration, without immersing the tip in the sample. Add the 100 µL of 0.2 M Na₃PO₄ solution, again using the same pipette tip for the three samples with the same concentration; homogenise the mixture in each well by gentle pipetting. Discard the tip.

10. Allow the samples to rest for 10 min while programming the absorbance reading in the equipment. A change of colour should be observed in all wells.
11. Measure the absorbance of the samples at 480 nm using the Multiskan Go spectrophotometer.
12. Calculate the iron concentration of the sample by plotting the absorbance of the standard samples vs concentration of the standard samples. Fit with a linear curve
13. Calculate the concentration of the unknown samples.

Note 9: Apply the dilution factor to get the real concentration of the original sample.